

Composite Inspection and Certification (CIC) System for Cybersecurity Assessment of ICT Products, Services, and Processes

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Abstract—The Digital Business Ecosystem (DBE) is heavily relied on digital technology to create business opportunities and supports analyzing wide range of data that flows through the business ecosystem. However, interconnected ICT components including products, services and processes within DBE raises security challenges due to the vulnerabilities within the components and technologies used by these components are mostly from third party providers. Additionally, cyber-attacks propagate throughout the whole digital networks creating major outage or disruption in the daily business or services operations and triggering far-reaching cascading effects into other segments and outcomes. Cybersecurity certification scheme can play a significant role in ensuring the security and trust of ICT products, services and processes. However, the conformity assessment process is challenging because product level security depends on not only the security of individual product but also interactions among the components used in the product itself. This paper presents a novel Composite Inspection and Certification (CIC) System that dynamically assess the conformity of the product based on the Composite target of evaluation. CIC includes a number of key components and facilitates the assessors in building their capacity for the overall certification process.

Keywords— *Cybersecurity certification, composite target of evaluation, conformity assessment, dynamic risk assessment, ICT product*

I. INTRODUCTION

A Digital Business Ecosystem (DBE) is a socio-technical network of individuals, organizations and technologies such as manufacturing that collectively co-create value which makes it possible to exploit Digital Servitization toward product-centric to a service-centric business models [1,2]. Hence, Digital Servitization presents various advantages unlocking new business opportunities, but it also raises several security challenges that may result in unforeseeable risks and threats. In particular, most of these

technologies (mainly from foreign manufacturers) often have multiple vulnerabilities and a high number of potential attack points (due to misconfiguration, high degree of interdependency, lack of effective security controls, limited or/and insecure accessibility etc.) increasing the cybersecurity challenge in the Age of Digital Transformation, as described in the 2019 ENISA report on Industry 4.0 Cybersecurity Challenges and Recommendations [3]. Cyber security certification plays an important role in increasing trust and security in ICT Products, ICT Services, and ICT Processes

Within this context, EU Cybersecurity Act (EUCSA) aims to lay down a framework for the establishment of European cybersecurity certification schemes for the purpose of ensuring an adequate level of cybersecurity for ICT products, services and processes[4]. This scheme aims to comply any ICT component using a robust Conformity Assessment (CA) process through compliance against specific selected security objectives and related applicable requirements. However, the CA process is continuously evolving and complex due to the interconnected ICT elements and composite Target of Evaluation (TOE) with unique and diverse requirements for each ICT object. The cybersecurity certification plays an important role in increasing trust and security in ICT Products, service and process. Similarly, Cyber Resilience Act (CRA) is also introduced which specifies that vulnerability handling process needs to be in place by the manufacturer, and attest that the services meet the essential requirements set out in y the CRA[17].

To address the aforementioned challenges, this paper presents a novel contribution for unique and dynamic conformity assessment of the connected ICT components. It proposes a collaborative Composite Inspection and Certification (CIC) system that delivers certification as a service, enabling the continuous monitoring, effective

assessment of the controls and the validation of the cybersecurity posture of the ICT products, services, and processes under evaluation. CIC considers conformity assessment as a composite evaluation process analysing the conformance to cybersecurity certification incorporating risk assessment and requirements analysis, verification and testing procedures that can be used by organisations to strengthen their security policy. The proposed CIC is a part of the European Union’s Horizon Europe Project, i.e., CUSTODES[15]. This paper provides an overview of CIC and it’s key components and demonstrates how the key stakeholders such as self-assessors, conformity assessment bodies, or any national cybersecurity certification authorities can interact with CIC for overall conformity assessment.

II. CYBERSECURITY CERTIFICATION FRAMEWORK

The cybersecurity certification framework generally provides a mechanism to establish certification schemes and attest that the ICT products, services and processes which have been evaluated in accordance with such schemes comply with specified security requirements as a means to protect the availability, authenticity, integrity or confidentiality of stored or transmitted or processed data or the functions or services offered by, or accessible via, those products, services and processes throughout their life cycle. In particular, the framework includes rules and criteria to preserve security of ICT element. For example, European Cybersecurity Certification Scheme is the Common Criteria based European candidate cybersecurity certification scheme (EUCC) [5] which looks into the certification of ICT products’ cybersecurity, based on the Common Criteria, the Common Methodology for Information Technology Security

Evaluation, and the corresponding standards ISO/IEC 15408 and ISO/IEC 18045 respectively. According to the EUCC, any applicable ICT Product [6], can be subject to a formal security evaluation also known as Conformity Assessment (CA) through which the compliance against specific selected security objectives and selected applicable requirements, (described either in a Security Profile or in a Target of Evaluation) is evaluated following a specific Cybersecurity Certification Scheme. A Target of Evaluation (TOE) could be a set of software, firmware and/or hardware possibly accompanied by guidance [7], whereas the Security Profiles (SPs) allow to define an implementation independent set of security requirements for categories of ICT products that meet specific needs [8]. Figure 1 presents an overview the certification scheme which specifies assurance level based on specific security requirements and profiles. The assessor performs the conformity assessment for the TOC of specific building block. In most cases these TOE consist of many heterogeneous primary objects named as ‘Building Blocks’ under evaluation (e.g. communication and network technologies, software and hardware appliances, ICT Services, ICT processes etc.) designed and manufactured by different companies and institutions, that exchange information through an interoperability architecture. These objects are layered and connected vertically and horizontally to form a Composite TOE. However, the complexity of Composite TOE grows exponentially based on a variety of factors, such as the number of the ‘Building Blocks’ used to build the platform, the set of the security functionalities implemented, the diversity of the applications, the number of security and business requirements covered.

Fig. 1. Cybersecurity Certification Scheme

III. Proposed Composite Inspection and Certification (CIC) System

The proposed CIC mainly contributes for an effective cybersecurity audit and certification process[15]. It aims to enhance control and trust of the composite products with coverage all the relevant areas of security and resilience. As stated the CIS system is based on the use of the composite TOE considering the results of the individual subsystem certification and combines to a set the level of Assurance Level for the whole certification process. Therefore, CIS system assumes that the composition may also reveal that

critical parts of the individual subsystems require re-testing due to the new context of usage within the composite TOE. This allows to reuse the information and evidence accompanying the certified building block to a certain extent during the evaluation of the composite TOE. The compositional security certification, i.e., certMILS, is a similar type of project which aims to provide affordable certification of composed systems through MILS Platform Protection Profile[16]. It also provides guidelines and templates for MILS certification. However, this proposed work differs from certMILS due to composite conformity

assessment process with composite ToE providers. This section provides an overview of the proposed CIC and key components.

Figure 2 presents the key components of the CIC System that implements a Composite Certification process with the ability to support the EU-wide cybersecurity certification framework [9]. This figure depicts how the concepts of risk management, testing, inspection and certification are used for a comprehensive conformity assessment according to ISO/IEC15408 and ISO/IEC18045[10,11]. It consists of six key components including i) Dynamic Risk Assessment

(DRA), ii) Composite Conformity Assessment Process (CCAP); iii) Restricted & Trusted Execution (RTE) Environment; (iv) the Security Audit/Security Testing (SA/ST), (v) Certificate Discovery (CerDisc); and (vi) Certification Sharing (CertS). The figure also demonstrates the interconnections that exist among these components and the relevant terms. These relations reveal the multi aspects and multiplicity of CIC i.e., it can be used to manage the cyber risks and generate the Security Profiles (SPs) of the Composite TOE, to assess the defined SPs' claims, and also to check and verify the conformity based on well-defined and trusted evidence and reused certification results.

Fig. 2. Composite Inspection and Certification (CIC) System

A. CIC Component Interactions

The CIC initiates through the Dynamic Risk Assessment (DRA) aims at providing a harmonized risk-based approach for identifying the security objectives and requirements in order to build the Security Profiles (SPs) of composite TOE. In particular, DRA will be used by the TOE providers to decompose the Composite TOE into building blocks under evaluation identifying the corresponding business requirements. The latter, together with the available certification schemes, standards and regulations drive the specification of the security objectives which are defined according to the assurance of the corresponding block and refine the relevant security requirements. All these are used as inputs to the risk assessment phases (risk analysis/evaluation) that feed the risk treatment-migration phase. The output of the risk treatment is a set of security functionalities and controls selected according to the defined security requirements. The proposed security measures will be used to generate the SPs of the composite TOE that are the basis for the conformity assessment performed by the Assessors.

Once the SP is defined by DRA, the assessors then use the Composite Conformity Assessment Process (CCAP) to evaluate the composite TOE against a set of security requirements defined in the relevant SPs. As the composite product is made up of building blocks that have additional software or hardware modules, therefore, the composite TOE's cybersecurity certification depends on the certification of each of its software and hardware. However, these blocks may have been certified by using different schemes and assurance levels. In order for the proposed approach to derive the security assurance level of a composite TOE, the relationship between the security assurance levels of the individual building block will be considered based on their

interactions and interconnections. To this end, the CCAP component incorporates and implements two sequential processes of conformity. Firstly a Building Blocks'-based certification (2B-C) process that relies on the testing capabilities of the Restricted & Trusted Execution (RTE) Environment to assess the security levels of the individual building blocks. This environment is operated by the assessor (e.g. 3rd party stakeholders and regulators like Conformity Assessment Bodies (CABs)) and is deployed in the TOE providers (e.g. manufacturer) establishing a trusted environment between them that accelerates and facilitates the testing, inspection, audit and (re-) certification of the TOE. In order to meet its objectives, it provides a dynamic and real-time evaluation of the security and resilience of each devices and subsystems, i.e. building blocks as well as the TOE as a whole incorporating a set security testing layers (e.g. Security Assessment, Static Application Security Testing and Hardware Security Assessment Capabilities) available in the Security Audit/Security Testing (SA/ST) Component. It should be noted that if a building block has been certified by another assessor, the relevant certification evidence will be published in the publicly accessible Certification Registries of the Assessors, becoming accessible through the Certificate Discovery (CerDisc) Component. The aim of CerDisc is to facilitate the reuse of certification evidence, to further open-up the certification-related data and to increase transparency and consistency of the certification process. Then, the second process of conformity is the TOE-based certification (TOE-C) that aggregates and accumulates the results produced by the 2B-C process and evaluate them to determine whether all individual building blocks comprising the TOE meet the requirements of the corresponding SPs. This layer is responsible for calculating the assurance level of the composite TOE considering the assurance levels of the individual blocks.

Finally, the Certification Sharing (CertS) offers threat intelligence and Certification sharing capabilities, enabling collaboration, secure and privacy-aware exchange of information (e.g. discovered vulnerabilities, threats, risks and security incidents associated with the composite TOE between the Assessors, the TOE providers and other relevant third parties (e.g. Industry cooperation groups, CERTs, CSIRTs). In addition, the CertS Component provides a data-driven AI-based approach to continuously contextualise newly identified known risk/weakness/vulnerability associated with the TOE. All the security, risks and vulnerability related information associated with the Composite TOE that will be extracted from otherwise disparate and distributed sources will be fed to the other components (the DRA Component, the CCAP Component, the RTE Environment and the SA/ST Component) in order to help the assessors to grasp unique insights on possible cyber threats.

B. Dynamic Risk Assessment (DRA)

The cyberthreat landscape is continuously evolved with new attack surface and potential exploitation of published and zero day vulnerabilities[13,14]. In this context, DRA offers a dynamic evaluation of undesirable events that need to be prevented in a given Composite TOE. In order for the evaluation to be deemed effective and reliable in improving the security posture of the TOE, the operational environment in which the TOE is intended to operate and be used should be considered. This environment includes all the aspects associated with the security of the processes, techniques, and technologies associated with the TOE, including assumptions on the environment in which it will be used or will operate, the threat scenarios and threat agents that are relevant to its secure operation as well as the security controls that are applied to address all the relevant security requirements. A precise definition of these aspects is essential for specification of the goal, purpose and scope of the evaluation. A dynamic risk-based approach will be used to identify and assess risks associated with the Composite TOE before specifying requirements for the building blocks. This analysis will be based on threat models for both the composite and individual blocks. In particular, the adopted risk assessment process will identify and evaluate the potential risks and threats of disruption to the TOE and their building blocks considering their interdependencies. The proposed approach includes a number of security processes for threat assessment, risk estimation, impact analysis, risk propagation and mitigation. An event-driven risk analysis based on probabilistic and propagation models (e.g. attack-path, threats dependency chains) will be followed to formulate optimized defences and predict future risks. In this vein, a dynamic AI and ML based approach will be applied to further elaborate on the risk/defines results with evidence retrieved from open repositories through the Certification Sharing (CertS) Component.

The outcome of the risk mitigation process specifies different assurance levels (basic', 'substantial' or 'high') will be assigned to the composite TOE and the accompanying software and hardware building blocks, depending on the level of the risk associated with their intended use. The higher the potential impact of a disruption of a certain building

blocks', the more secure this block should be. Therefore, each assurance level incorporates a set of security requirements derived from the above hybrid Top-Down & Bottom-up Approach and include selected controls and security functionalities according to these requirements and the corresponding security objectives. Also, the assurance levels will be used to determine the level of stringency and depth of the evaluation that should be applied to the TOE and the different building blocks. The DRA Component will use a machine readable representation based on NIST OSCAL [12] to describe and model all the above mentioned elements (including controls/ requirements / objectives etc.) of the Composite TOE. The output of the above processes will be used to generate the SPs of the TOE that will be openly published via a publicly accessible Certification Registry in order to be reused by other interesting Stakeholders/Assessors/TOE Providers. These SPs will be fed to the CCAP Component in order for the composite TOE to be assessed following the guidelines set out there and against the claims found in the SPs. In this way, the DRA Component enables the creation of tailored and risk-based Security Profiles of the Composite TOE.

C. Composite Conformity Assessment Process (CCAP)

This component encapsulates and implements a relevant set of enforcement mechanisms to ground the confidence and provide the assurance that the composite TOE and the accompanying building blocks meet the security objectives and address the SFRs and the SARs stipulated in the corresponding SPs. It aims to support activities in order to ensure compliance and identify and mitigate potential compliance breaches. To this end, the component adopts and implements a structured process that facilitates the partial and continuous assessment and lean re-certification of the composite products in accordance with the relevant principles, standards, regulations and schemes. From a technical perspective, this process relies on a machine-readable approach to describe the given individual validation activities and the level of rigour and depth of the evaluation process defined in the SPs produced by the DRA Component.

CCAP considers both post-market monitoring and ex-ante conformity assessments activities will be established and conducted to specify the composite assurance level of the TOE throughout their lifespans. Through the Ex-ante conformity assessments activities, an ex-ante compliance check of the composite TOE with all relevant requirements will be accomplished before the product will be placed on the market. In contrast, the post-market monitoring activities check the ex-post compliance with the guidelines as outlined by SPs and the corresponding schemes. Thus, even if the composite TOE is continuously evolved to meet the corresponding changes, these ex-post activities ensure they remain secure and compliant throughout their lifecycle. However, it should be noted that these different types of ex-post and ex-ante assessments are not mutually exclusive but rather crucially complementary, producing the proofs and the evidence required to identify the nature and the extent of the security functionalities implementation/applicability. In particular, both of them are necessary to cover the whole TOE lifecycle

and ensure robustness and sustainability of the testing and certification.

D. *Restricted & Trusted Execution (RTE)*

The proposed CIC system provides a novel virtualization-based RTE Environment using Digital Twins for the secure configuration, deployment, operation and verifiable auditing of the composite TOEs. This environment is a core element of the CIC System, and address the trust concerns regarding IPR, confidentiality, trade secrets while also reducing the time and efforts required for (re-) certification. The RTE Environment, even if is operated by the assessors, will be deployed to the providers to conduct self-assessments throughout the lifecycle of their composite TOEs offerings a secure and reliable self-assessment approach for discovering security flaws and weaknesses and for identifying resistance against a set of cyber threats and risks. However, self-testing relies heavily on the active involvement of the TOE providers, thus RTE will include the necessary security countermeasures against the adversarial, malicious or negligent behavior on their parts. To this end, this environment will implement novel OSS (NFVs, NFVI and VIM) trust extensions, leveraging root of trust capabilities that guarantees and simplifies the trust relationships between the assessor and the TOE providers, thus, providing strong security and trust claims on the trustworthiness of their self-assessments. The aim of this process is to support an extended trust aware evaluation approach, for distributed auditing, that enhances and augments the trustworthiness and credibility of the testing results. Also, there will be specific attestation policies generated in order to achieve the required level of trust, trustworthiness and reliability assurance of the self-assessments testing.

E. *Security Audit/Security Testing (SA/ST)*

The SA/ST component incorporates a set of well-calibrated auditing tools required to conduct the validation checks defined in the SPs of the composite TOEs in order to demonstrate that they comply with the relevant requirements. Such checking performs a vulnerability analysis to detect known vulnerabilities and in parallel also applies fine-grained innovative security testing techniques to identify unknown vulnerabilities and contribute the results to the security community and other third parties. This component in contrast to existing solutions linked to existing open-source repositories and program types, is following a testing approach that orchestrates several different types of security testing mechanisms (adapted to Testing layers) that are able to detect vulnerabilities. The bulk of the security testing is performed either at design and development phase or during the deployment and operation stage. In particular, the SA/ST includes different test types including security assessment, static application security testing and hardware security assessment.

F. *Certificate Discovery (CerDisc)*

This component provides a mechanism for publishing and discovering certification related information in order to increase trust and transparency among different certification-related stakeholders, including manufacturers and products' providers. The component enables and leverages the exploration, discovery, and sharing of descriptions

through publicly accessible certification registries of assessors. In this context, the CerDisc implements two main functionalities. The first one is the certificate publisher which provides methods to automatically generate machine-readable descriptions of certified TOE and blocks based specific standardized format and assist with the generation of human-readable information. certificate publisher will be responsible to manage these descriptions and transform it into linked unified data structures that are easily discoverable, combinable and in an appropriate format to be openly published and reused by other Assessors. For the certification process, an interface will be built to support the representation of the results produced by the CCAP Component. The second functionality is the certificate discovery and consumption engine that allows the discovery, acquisition, processing and interpretation of certificate-related information from the publicly accessible Certification Registries of the Assessors in order to be easily consumable by the CIC system. This engine provides the basis for re-using data structures and discovering the relationships among existing standards, certification schemas and targets under evaluation. To this end, existing advanced and proven linkage-based techniques will be used to indicate the interlinking between published certificate-related data structures with the different aspects of the composite TOE.

G. *Certification Sharing (CertS)*

CertS offers threat intelligence and certification sharing capabilities, enabling collaboration, secure and privacy-aware information transport between TOE manufactures/providers, the Assessors and third parties. They will undertake the identification, dissemination and sharing of the right privacy-preserving and sanitized information in reusable and interoperable standards and/or formats (such as STIX). Privacy preserving is another important issue which will be considered at every phase of sharing, applying methods such as anonymization or pseudo anonymization and encryption techniques incorporated. The CertS Component exchanges risks, threats, vulnerabilities and incident-related information as well as compliance breaches discovered from all precedent components. In this context, the CertS Component adopts a dynamic data collection of heterogeneous information consisting of (i) threat intelligence feeds from external and internal sources (both public and private), including data that may be provided by other Assessors, manufacturers and various European CSIRT networks; (ii) General unstructured threat intelligence from relevant e.g., web pages, blogs and social media conversations; and (iii) Structured Data from Open Source (e.g. National Vulnerability Database (NVD)). Also, the CertS Component implements a data-driven AI-based approach to continuously contextualise newly identified known risk/weakness/vulnerability associated with the TOE.

IV. CONCLUSION

Cybersecurity certification scheme certainly raises the organization's confidence and consumer's trust of using their products. However, there is a growing gap in existing cybersecurity certification schemes in providing the criteria of conformity assessments which establish the degree of adherence of composite ICT products, services and processes, comprising multiple interconnected primary assets and resources towards specific requirements across their overall

lifecycle. Additionally, the conformity assessment process is challenging due to the dependency of interconnected ICT elements and composite Target of Evaluation (TOE) with diverse requirements for each ICT object. The proposed Composite Inspection and Certification (CIC) System aims to fulfil this gap by designing and developing a Composite Certification & Conformity Assessment Approach which will evaluate and ensure that composite ICT products, services and processes (Composite TOE) encompassing heterogeneous primary objects. The proposed CIC consists of six components which cover all aspects of compliance assessment from extraction of security profile using dynamic risk assessment, composite conformity assessment, security testing to certificate discovery and sharing. This paper provides an overview of CIC systems and each components. However, CIC needs to be implemented into a specific composite supply chain context to demonstrate its applicability. Additionally, we are also planning to adopt existing tool to automate individual component of the CIC system.

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